

A Study on Challenges of Teachers' Role Stress in School Education

¹Dr. V. SUMATHY

ABSTRACT -- *The globalization and denationalization of the tutoring system in different countries and in India forced the higher education to be more competent so as to produce the participants with better understanding, accommodativeness, skills and competencies which are essential for survival in the world market. In tune with this, the Indian education system had undergone rapid changes in terms of development, privatization, marketization, curricular reforms and instructive innovations. These changes have confronted the universities in terms of quality teaching, shortage of faculty of high ability, ineffective teaching methods, outdated curriculum and evaluation system, lack of suitable reading materials, poor set-up facilities, faulty administration, faculty admission criteria, inability to attract and retain talented minds and absence of academically conducive atmosphere. Further, the increasing role frolicked by latest knowledge, services, innovation and research in economic growth and development, the emergence of the information society and the need for quality education results in enlarged pressure on the advanced education system and teachers in particular. These factors in-turn unfavorably affects the quality of our education system and creates various stressors and strain in teachers which further declines their presentation.*

Key words-- *Role stress, teachers' role, school education, work-life imbalance, work stress, human resource management, etc.*

I. INTRODUCTION

For fluctuating the globalizing world, the role of the teachers is indispensable to improve the supportable education. At the same time, inspiring and guiding the students in increasing employability assistances with the digital tools is the requirement for a teacher. Thus, a teacher in the twenty-first era will be a digital teacher. Teachers are not the expediter for learning of the students only, and now they are responsible for training the students for increasing employability skills, expanding the mind, growing digital citizenships, critical thinking, and creativity as well as sustainable learning. Thus, the winning of the students is the win of the teachers. With the passes of time and integration of technology in every sector, the teacher's role has changed a lot. They need to enrich some skills to develop their students. Otherwise, the learners will not get the lesson, and it will upsurge of educated jobless in the digital era.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, Thiru Kolanjiyappar Government Arts College, Vriddhachalam - 606 001, Tamil Nadu

The stressors that causes teachers stress are divided in to four major categories, the below figure shows the conceptual framework of job stress.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Job Stress

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To measure the level of job stress among school teachers.
 2. To find out the influence of personal factors on the level of job stress among school teachers.
 3. To study the impact of family factors on the level of job stress among school teachers.
 4. To analyze the role of organizational factors on the level of job stress among school teachers.
- To compare the level of job stress among public and private school teachers.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN

A descriptive research design was used to investigate levels of job stress, personal strain, and coping resources reported by public, private-aided, private-unaided school teachers in Cuddalore district. Comparative analysis was conducted to investigate differences in teachers' stress among the type of school they belong.

V. VARIABLES CHOSEN

After studying the literatures based on the research teachers' job stress, it is clear from the literature that teachers in this profession are experiencing various degrees of stress due to several factors. There are six major

variables that are identified to play a major role in influencing stress among teachers in Cuddalore district. These variables are turnover intension, organizational climate, and individual demands at work, teachers' effectiveness, family work conflict, and work family conflict. Teacher stress variables, coping strategies, some demographic variables are also included in the present study. In order to identify the influence of these variables both dependent and independent variables are taken for this research.

Segmentation of teachers' job stress

This method attempts to identify relatively standardized groups of cases based on the selected characteristics, using an algorithm that can handle large numbers of cases. The teachers' job stress can be classified into three categories based on stress level they have on supervisory support, role ambiguity, role stress, organizational management, jobs satisfaction, life satisfaction and task stress. The teachers' job stress is classified into three segments because the difference among the coefficients is significant only on three cases on the hierarchical cluster. For the persistence of job stress, K-Means cluster is used.

Table 1: Final Cluster Centers

Stress Level	Cluster					
	1	Rank	2	Rank	3	Rank
Supervisory support	4.03	I	3.18	II	2.53	III
Role ambiguity	4.41	I	3.50	II	2.37	III
Role stress	4.01	II	4.39	I	2.99	III
Organizational management	3.95	I	3.91	II	2.57	III
Jobs satisfaction	4.32	I	3.32	II	3.05	III
Life satisfaction	4.23	I	3.11	II	2.57	III
Task stress	4.06	I	2.61	II	2.49	III
Average	4.14		3.43		2.65	

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows the mean values of all the teachers' job stress factors are in the three final clusters. The mean values of teachers' job stress in the final clusters centers table reflect the attributes of each cluster. It is also noted from the table that no particular stress factors is heavily loaded on any particular cluster segment. Table portrays that the teachers' job stress can be divided into three distinct clusters based on their response. These clusters may be designated as "high level of stress", "medium level of stress" and "low level of stress". The rank of the clusters on teachers' job stress is given in the above table. The description of the characteristics of all the three clusters or segments along with the label is given below.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance

Stress Level	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	DF	Mean Square	DF		
Supervisory support	75.52	2	0.18	387	417.41	0.00
Role ambiguity	143.78	2	0.13	387	1.04E3	0.00
Role stress	74.32	2	0.21	387	353.78	0.00
Organizational management	88.84	2	0.13	387	653.63	0.00
Jobs satisfaction	56.28	2	0.24	387	226.24	0.00
Life satisfaction	92.45	2	0.17	387	540.45	0.00
Task stress	92.33	2	0.21	387	423.51	0.00

Source: Primary Data.

The above table shows that the three clusters differ in mean value of all the seven criteria. But the ANOVA table indicates that the difference exists among the three clusters in the mean values of seven aspects of stress level factors are significant. The significant value for all stress level factor is 0.00. This indicates that the mean values of all the seven perceptions are significantly different among three clusters. This also means that all the seven stress factors are influencing significantly in dividing people into three segments based on stress levels.

Table 3: Number of Cases in Each Cluster

Cluster	1	110.00	28.20%
	2	107.00	27.44%
	3	173.00	44.36%
Valid		390.00	

Source: Primary Data.

The number of cases in each cluster table indicates that around 110 teachers out of 390 teachers are in cluster I which is the high level of stress group and 107 out of 390 teachers are in medium level of stress group. This means that around 28.20 per cent of teachers are in high level of stress segment and 27.44 per cent of teachers are in medium level of stress group. In cluster three, 44.36 per cent of the teachers are comes under low level of stress group

VI. COMMUNALITY

Communality tells us what proportion of each variance is shared with the factors which have been created. Basically higher communalities are better to formulate models and it should be above 0.50 to be acceptable. If the communalities are below 0.50, it will struggle to load significantly on any factors and it is advisable to

remove such variables from the analysis. Communality is the sum of squared factor loading for all factors for a given variable in the row.

Table 4: Communality

S. No.	Variables	Communalities
Individual demands at work		
1	Quantitative demands	0.63
2	Cognitive demands	0.87
3	Work pace	0.75
4	Emotional demands	0.64
5	Demands for hiding emotions	0.70
Teachers' job stress		
1	Supervisory support	0.79
2	Role ambiguity	0.70
3	Role Stress	0.69
4	Organizational management	0.83
5	Jobs satisfaction	0.76
6	Life satisfaction	0.93
7	Task stress	0.76

It can be observed from Table 4 that the communality value in respect of all the factors studied is above the minimum required value of 0.50, and hence a valid CFA model can be arrived at.

VII. CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) involves the requirement and estimation of one or more conjectured models of factor structure, each of which proposes a set of latent variables to account for covariance's among a set of experiential variables. Linear structural equation modeling can be used to test the fit of a hypothesized model against the sample data. Before testing the hypotheses and evaluating the full structural model, it is critical to test the validity of the constructs. Structural equation modeling could be a system, which effectively counts a whole range of distinctive multivariate analysis systems, including regression, factor analysis and analysis of variance. A structural equation model thus consists of two components, the "measurement model", in which latent variables (theoretical constructs) are proposed and tested through confirmatory factor analysis, and the "structural model", throughout that the theories square measure coupled on by means of hypotheses in associate extremely social approach. The measurement model is based on a priori information, from exploratory factor analysis, about the data structure. The measurement model, then, represents the CFA. This model specifies the pattern by which each measure loads on a particular factor or unobserved variable

Table 5: Goodness of Fit Indices

Indices	Goodness of fit
---------	-----------------

	Individual demand at work	Teachers job stress
Chi-square (χ^2)	8.88	13.09
Degrees of freedom (df)	2	5
Probability level (p)	0.01177	0.02257
Normed chi-square (χ^2/df)	4.44	2.618
Goodness-of-fit (GFI)	0.90	0.90
Adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI)	0.99	0.99
Incremental index of fit (IFI)	0.99	0.99
Tucker-Lewis index (TLI)	0.95	0.95
Comparative fit index (CFI)	0.96	0.96
Root mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA) 90% confidence interval ranging from 0.05 to 0.10	0.094	0.068

Table 5 portrays the results of independent measurement model confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The individual demand at work CFA and teachers' job stress CFA is to verify the factor structure as proposed. All factor loadings were highly significant, which demonstrate that the chosen generic questions for each latent variable reflect a single underlying construct. The GFI value is well exceeding the recommended 0.90 threshold level. RMSEA for our measurement mode for individual demand at work of CFA (0.96), which is in the range of 0.08 and 0.10 and thus indicates mediocre fit and teachers' job stress CFA (0.068) which is in the range of 0.05 and 0.08 and thus indicates fair fit. To conclude, the results indicate an acceptable overall fit between the model and the observed data. All other fit measures, contain NFI, CFI, IFI, GFI and AGFI, also show acceptable (> 0.90) results.

Figure 1: Confirmatory Factor Analysis for the variable Individual Demands at work

Table 6: Confirmatory Factor Analysis for the Variable Individual Demands at Work

Variable	Standard Solutions	T - Value	Error Variance	R ²
Cognitive demands	0.90	18.04	0.13	0.67
Work pace	0.98	18.37	0.43	0.69
Emotional demands	0.98	19.39	0.62	0.74
Demands for hiding emotions	0.78	14.60	0.51	0.50

Chi-Square=13.09, df=5, P-value=0.02257, RMSEA=0.068

Figure 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis for the Teacher Stress Variables

Table 7: Confirmatory Factor Analysis for the Teacher Stress Variables

Variable	Standard Solutions	T - Value	Error Variance	R ²
Supervisory support	0.67	15.79	0.12	0.35
Role ambiguity	0.72	17.54	0.35	0.55
Role stress	0.66	18.38	0.15	0.53
Organizational management	0.64	14.44	0.12	0.55
Jobs satisfaction	0.80	16.66	0.01	0.69
Life satisfaction	0.72	18.94	0.18	0.44

VIII. STRUCTURAL MODEL AND HYPOTHESES TESTING

Having checked construct validity for all of the factors, the path relationships depicted in the theoretical model developed were further analysed using the SEM software LISREL8.72. The assessment of the theoretical model using SEM criteria was considered appropriate for a number of reasons. First, SEM allows for a simultaneous examination of all the proposed hypotheses. Second, the testing of the fully specified model allows us to examine which construct or constructs are driving the relationships with the quality reliability variables.

Third, in SEM, the overall fit of the model provides an indication of the validity of the proposed conceptual model. Finally, SEM is a natural extension of the confirmatory factor analysis. The results may be summed up as follows: $X^2=18.96$; $df=5$; $p=0.0196$. Since the P value is less than the desired minimum of 0.05, it can be said that the model fails to fit in the real wisdom. However, a strong X^2 value with large sample size provides scope for employing other tests and the value of such goodness-of-fit measures in respect of such tests are displayed as under: RMSEA = 0.089. RMSEA not more than 0.05 denotes good fit; RMSEA ranging from 0.05 to 0.08 denotes a fair fit; RMSEA ranging from 0.08 to 0.10 denotes mediocre fit. Hence, the mediocre fitness of the model is established. GFI = 0.98; AGFI = 0.94; CFI = 0.99; NFI = 0.98. This signifies the mediocre fitness of the model. Hence, the results confirm the acceptability of the derived model.

Chi-Square=18.96, df=5, P-value=0.00196, RMSEA=0.089

Figure 3: Structural Equation Model

Hypothesis states that individual demands at work are positively related to the strength of the relationship with teachers' job stress factors. The corresponding t-value (4.55) is significant at the 0.1 % level. Based on this result, hypothesis is supported.

IX. CONCLUSION

Education is the source by which knowledge or the cultural store house can be transfer from one generation to another. Education is that constructive process which drags a person out from darkness, poverty and misery and leads him on the polls of enlightenment, prosperity and happiness by developing his individuality in all its aspects i.e. physical, mental, emotional and social. He becomes answerable, active, ingenious and adventurous civilian of a strong and good ethical character. Education is process of growth in which the specific is helped out to develop his aptitude, authority, curiosity and goals. The evolvment of the country rest on the quality of teachers, constructing, tools, instructional factual, up-to-date archive, well developed prospectus, etc.

REFERENCE

1. Natarajan, C., & Renu Vij (2011). A study on stress level of working females of multinational financial institutions in Chandigarh city. *Res Manageria*, 2 (4), 42-45.
2. Natarajan, C., & Vijai, C. (2014). An empirical review on the work stress of employees in Life Insurance Corporation of India. Madurai: Shanalax Publications, 34-41.
3. Natarajan, C., & Vijai, C. (2015). Work stress among women employees in IT sector: An empirical study. *The Indian Pages: International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6-13.
4. Ransford, et al. (2009). The role of teachers' psychological experiences and perceptions of curriculum supports on the implementation of a social and emotional learning curriculum. *School Psychology Review*, 38, 510-532.
5. Renu Vij., & Natarajan, C. (2011). A study on the occupational stress among bank employees in Chandigarh. *People's Journal of Management*, 1 (4), 30-35.
6. Renu Vij., & Natarajan, C. (2011). Analysis of role hierarchy and role stress as predictors of job satisfaction: A study among life insurance employees. Bangkok: Planetary Scientific Research Centre, 618-620.
7. Yoon, J. S. (2002). Teacher characteristics as predictors of teacher student relationships: Stress, negative effect, and self-efficacy. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 30, 485-494.
8. Yousef, D. A. (2002). Job satisfaction as a mediator of the relationship between role stressors and organizational commitment: A study from an Arabic cultural perspective. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 17, 250-266.